

TEACHING LISTENING THROUGH AUTHENTIC MATERIALS

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Annotation: This article is devoted to applying authentic materials in teaching listening and usage of authentic materials in listening courses could motivate students, draw their interests and stimulate them into language learning process. Additionally, authentic resources open the doors of real world in learning and acquiring target language. As a result, students can create language environment like native users and they are able to listen recordings for specific purposes. So, interesting authentic materials would develop learners' listening abilities in language lessons and language usage in natural world.

Key words: direct method, imitating, valuable source, interrelate, conventional way, utilizing, audio-lingual approach, grammar-translation approach, crucial skill, discourse.

Communicative language teaching has changed artificial classrooms to authentic educational places by connecting language classroom with real materials of social world. The usage of authentic materials in teaching have a great influence in acquiring language skills effectively. For example, the usage of real-life sources, such as movies, BBC news, radio materials or songs would help to develop learners' listening skills in teaching English in current classrooms. Therefore, the usage of authentic sources in listening has become modern trend with the improvement of different technologies, such as the Internet and they are especially applied in listening courses.

In early approaches of teaching language, authentic materials were not considered as valuable source because they were nor arranged in teaching

objectives. Actually, several traditional approaches of language learning were explained as useful ways in teaching English. One of the earliest method of teaching language was grammar-translation approach and it includes two aspects, such as grammar and lexical comprehension [1:p.112]. Students were taught the grammar with vocabulary, writing could be done automatically during this process and listening was not needed since the grammar translation method was understood as a set of exact rules and studied as a form. Then direct method was existed and learners acquired language orally but listening was not recognized as crucial skill. In grammar-approach listening was an important part of language learning but it was considered as classroom-based activity and it was not related to real world. Only in the middle of twentieth century audio-lingual approach became well-known and the early objective was correct pronunciation. Students were supposed to listen examples of natural pronunciation and corrected grammatical mistakes before imitating the voice of native speaker.

For the last decades, the main aim of a foreign language teaching has shifted from teaching correct grammar and pronunciation into communicative language teaching and learning. Students have been learnt meaning and function instead of language form and they are able to apply classroom theories to authentic situations. Moreover, the usage of language in real-life situations and implementing authentic resources are demands of current methodology. It is described that English is a global language and a lot of users are non-native speakers. Therefore, correct pronunciation and grammar rules are nor wanted today. Current speakers prefer to communicate rather than grammar forms in applying target language.

Authentic materials are considered as one of the most crucial attribute of authenticity and they are recognized as the base of any classroom process. The usage of authentic language in one lesson plays a fundamental role for attracting learners compared with other features of language learning [2:p.78]. According to Dewi's experiment, there were listening problems of several students in their listening comprehension and their points do not reach Minimum Passing Grade as

well in researcher's macro teaching. Because English is a foreign even now and the second cause is that speaking skills could not run well without listening comprehension. The next reason was to find out successful materials to develop learner's listening comprehension. Usually, teachers apply listening materials in conventional way. They sometimes read the sources in the process of learning listening and students are supposed to rewrite what they heard from their tutor. This make the learners feel bored and they lost their interests about developing listening skills [3:p.56]. Therefore, teachers should use effective materials during their practice of listening comprehension to attract learners attention, to interest them in developing their skills.

According to Liu, current English teachers should apply following pedagogical implications:

- language teachers should aware of the term authenticity and understand the strong and weak points of utilizing them in English lessons. Authentic models could help students to develop their speaking as a natural, to draw their interest in real usage of foreign language and to make relations between classroom environment and outside situations. If tutors understand the qualities of utilizing the authentic materials, they could overcome their teaching problems of using effective sources;

- during the usage of authentic materials in listening lessons, teachers would be a chance to sequence tasks from simple to complicated. Utilizing authentic listening resources in classes could lead students to increase their phonological features of natural language. All textbooks of listening are not appropriate for different levels of students. Making needs analysis for various learners and adapting original materials are teachers' jobs. Material adaptation could be an effective method of making broad usage of real source, tutoring learners to understand the whole discourse and improving their language abilities by creating their confidence to study;

- teachers should be always worry about learning from literary sources or

getting information from pedagogical world. It is predicted that there could be another type of authenticity in the literary world or there might be an efficient way to interrelate authentic source and assignment in language groups. Additionally, teachers should be busy with reading the new literature in foreign language teaching, trying to overcome current problems of utilizing authentic materials in teaching. (Liu, 2016). This way could gradually improve their teaching abilities, improve teaching practice and research methods.

The usage of authentic materials in listening courses could motivate students, draw their interests and stimulate them into language learning process. Additionally, authentic resources open the doors of real world in learning and acquiring target language. As a result, students can create language environment like native users and they are able to listen recordings for specific purposes. So, interesting authentic materials would develop learners' listening abilities in language lessons and language usage in natural world.

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